

S1 Table : Bacterial strains used and their susceptibility profile to antibiotics.

	Microorganisms	Resistant	Intermediate	Sensitive
Gram negative	<i>Achromobacter xylosoxidans</i> 4892	TR, NIT, TE, FO	CAC, CAZ	CTR, AMC, IPM, CIP, AMP
	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> 5841	TR	TE, CAC	NIT, CTR, AMC, FO, CAZ, IPM, CIP, AMP
	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i> 426	CAZ, CAC, AMP		NIT, TE, CTR, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP, TR
	<i>Enterococcus cloacae</i> 6392	AMP, TR	NIT,	TE, CTR, AMC, FO, CAZ, IPM, CAC, CIP,
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> M17	To all		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> 1449	TE, CTR, CAZ, CAC, AMP, TR		NIT, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25922	To all		
	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> 3003	TE, AMP, TR	CAZ, CAC	NIT, CTR, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> 1449	AMP	NIT, CAZ, CAC	TE, CTR, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP, TR
	<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i> 4222	NIT, AMP	CAZ, TR	TE, CTR, AMC, FO, CAC, IPM, CIP
	<i>Morganella morganii</i> 1543	TE, FO, AMP, TR	NIT	CTR, AMC, CTR, CAZ, IPM, CAC, CIP
	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> 1543	TE, TR	AMP	NIT, AMC, CTR, FO, CAZ, IPM, CAC, CIP,
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> 3057	NIT, TE, AMP, TR	CAZ	CTR, AMC, FO, CAC, CIP
	<i>Serratia marsescens</i> 6441	NIT, AMP		TE, CTR, AMC, FO, CAZ, IPM, CAC, CIP, TR
Gram positive	<i>Corynebacterium spp</i> 1638	FO, CAZ, CAC, AMP, TR		NIT, TTE, CTR, AMC, IPM, CIP
	<i>Enterococcus avium</i> 1669	TE, AMP, TR	CIP	NIT, CTR, AMC, FO, CAZ, IPM, CAC,
	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> 5960	TE, AMP, TR	CAZ,	NIT, CTR, AMC, FO, IMP, CAC, CIP
	<i>Kocuria rizophilis</i> 1542	NIT, TE, CAZ, CAC, AMP		CTR, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP, TR

	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> 1449	CAZ, CAC, AMP, TR	NIT	TE, CTR, AMC, FO, IPM, CIP
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	To all		

AMC=amoxiclav, CAZ=ceftazidime, CAC= ceftazidime/clavulanic acid, CTR=ceftriaxone; CIP=ciprofloxacin, FO=fosfomycin, IMP=imipenem, NIT=nitrofurantoin, TE=tetracycline and TR=trimethoprim.